

Influence of Rotor Position in the Broadband Impedance Response for SFRA Rotating Machine Diagnosis

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Abstract—Sweep Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA) applied to rotating machine diagnosis and monitoring lacks of widespread industrial applicability up to this date. Several authors identify the rotor position influence as one of the main obstacles for an on-site and reliable diagnosis. This work provides a thorough investigation on how the rotor affects the broadband impedance for different rotor topologies. The rotor DC field is identified as a strong influence on the measured broadband impedance. First, a theoretical analysis is performed to study the effect of an external DC field in the broadband impedance. Then, a 4.7 kW PMSM is thoroughly analyzed including magnetostatic Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and experimental measurements. Finally, the influence of magnetic remanence on the broadband impedance is experimentally studied. To this aim, two induction machines with two different rotor types (i.e., wound-rotor and squirrel cage) are analyzed. This collection of results is aimed to clarify the physics behind the rotor position influence and to enhance the reliability of SFRA diagnosis for rotating machinery.

Index Terms—fault diagnosis, frequency response analysis, high-frequency

I. INTRODUCTION

Sweep Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA) is a standardized technique currently utilized for power transformer on-site diagnosis. Some of the most common scenarios when SFRA is applied are the transformer installation or relocation, factory short-circuit testing, and protocol diagnostic measurements [1]. The working principle of this technique is founded on the broadband measurement (i.e., from few Hz to the MHz band) of the impedance or admittance of the specimen under test, which resembles a RLC circuit. The different measurements taken over the transformer lifetime are compared to a baseline reference, which represents the healthy state of the machine. The differences with respect the baseline reference point out different faults or malfunction indicators.

The application of SFRA in the context of rotating machines remains confined to research studies and lacks standardization as of yet. Since the early 2000s several authors explored the application of SFRA to detect phase-to-phase and inter-turn short circuits in low-voltage stator windings [2]. This research trend continued throughout the years in works such as [3], [4], where SFRA is utilized to detect faults in low-voltage induction machines. Lamarre et al. [5] propose the SFRA to detect insulation ageing and discusses the advantages of winding reversal in hydro generators. The utility of this technique to detect winding ageing is extended in [6]

and [7], where the variation of impedance curves is studied under different insulation ageing mechanisms (e.g., thermal, moisture presence, etc.). Another research trend consists of the application of SFRA to detect short-circuit failures in salient poles of synchronous machines [8], [9]. Off-line SFRA represents a promising technique for many diagnosis and condition monitoring scenarios. The main advantage lays on the adaptability and rapidity of the test, exhibiting high cost-effectiveness mostly for MVA-ranged machines. The main obstacles towards methodology standardization are related to the lack of expertise on different faults and ageing impact, and on the method sensitivity to the machine geometry and rotor position [10].

The on-line variant of SFRA offers the advantage of continuous monitoring of the winding electrical signature. Sant'Ana et al. [11] presents a directly connected coupling that allows the on-line connection of the measurement apparatus. In [12] the work is extended by utilizing an active cancellation technique. A different solution is proposed in [13], where a cost effective solution is proposed for equipment passive coupling for on-line SFRA. The main drawback of on-line SFRA is the noisiness of the results that may be derived from electromagnetic couplings or from the effect of the rotor position in the inductive frequency bands. This noise may heavily mask the ageing and failure indicators in the broadband electrical signature.

The rotor position effect represents one of the main uncertainties for both off-line and on-line SFRA application. Platero et al. [14] present the variation of the single phase admittance curves induced by the rotor position displacement. The authors link the rotor position influence to the variation of the airgap and state that SFRA must be performed at a reference rotor position to avoid false diagnosis. The same phenomenon is observed in [15], where the phase impedance of an induction machine is measured with and without the rotor. In [16], the authors demonstrate that machines with constant airgap (i.e., cylindrical rotor induction machine) are also influenced by the rotor position. Kang et al. [17] analyse the effect of the induction machine rotor on the surge penetration (i.e., closely linked to the broadband impedance) while exploring its influence in partial discharge testing. The authors conclude that only closed-slot rotors in induction machines present significant remanent flux affecting their results. In addition, they take into account magnetic viscosity (i.e., slow relaxation of magnetization over time). A more recent work shows the

three phases broadband impedance measurement for a low-voltage randomly-wound induction machine, where a clear difference in the inductive band between phases is observed [18]. The authors link the impedance difference between phases to the randomness of coil turn location. However, the rotor position influence assessment is not performed. All these research results point out that the rotor position induces a variation on the inductance over the different frequency bands. Different causes for this effect are discussed in [16], but no conclusion is provided. One of the most feasible causes is derived from the effect of the rotor field, which may be present as material remanence even if no magnets or field winding are present [19]. This is supported by Roger et al. [20], who demonstrates the variation of the inductance for iron cores under a constant large valued dc field over a broad frequency band. In addition, the field penetration in the iron core for high-frequency small signal excitation is normally reduced and the flux may not penetrate the core. This causes the inductance of the stator winding to dramatically decrease at increased frequencies.

The present work is aimed to clarify the effect of the rotor position on the stator broadband impedance for SFRA diagnosis purposes. It expands the recent work presented in [21]. The phase-to-phase broadband impedance is mainly targeted due to its dominant inductive behaviour. However, the Common-Mode (CM) impedance is also analysed since the main resonance is directly influenced by the inductive terms. A 4.7 kW 8/12 concentrated winding Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) is utilized as a main case study specimen. The geometry and some material properties of this machine are known, which enable a detailed and thorough analysis. In addition, the effect of the rotor remanence is studied for both squirrel cage and slotted wound-rotor induction machines. The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the analytical study of the broadband impedance of a coil surrounded by a laminated iron core under DC external field excitation. Section III describes the analysis of the PMSM including magnetostatic Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and experimental measurements. Section IV presents the rotor position experimental analysis for two different types of induction machines (i.e., squirrel cage and wound-rotor induction motors). Section V presents a thorough discussion of the results across the three studied specimens. Finally, Section VI poses the main conclusions and future work directions.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The main aim of the present section is to analytically relate the stator winding broadband impedance to the dc flux imposed by the rotor magnets. The stator winding of a rotating electrical machine resembles a RLC circuit. Some examples of detailed broadband physical representations of windings are found in [22], [23]. The parasitic capacitance between stator winding and rotor is very small compared to the winding-to-ground or inter-turn capacitances and thus, the rotor mainly affects the series inductances and resistances. These are frequency dependent due to several phenomena linked to the skin and proximity effects in the conductors and the

Fig. 1. Single lamination geometry, magnetic field strength and current density distribution for high-frequency magnetic excitation [23]

laminated iron core [24]. At certain frequency, eddy currents flowing within single laminations become significant, creating a reaction field that shields the main magnetic field within the slot. To analytically study the effect of the laminated iron core in the broadband series frequency dependent resistance and inductance, a single lamination geometry is considered as depicted in Figure 1 [23]. The one-dimensional solution for the y-component of the magnetic field strength along the z-axis is provided by [25]:

$$\overline{H_y(z)} = H_0 \frac{\cosh(kz)}{\sinh(kb)} \quad (1)$$

where $\overline{H_y(z)}$ is the magnetic field amplitude in y direction along the z-axis, H_0 is the rms surface magnetic field value in the edges of the lamination when $z = b$, k is the complex term defined as $(1 - j)/\delta$, and δ is the penetration depth $\delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi f \sigma \mu}}$. Thus, the magnetic flux flowing within a single lamination assuming perfect insulation between iron sheets is given by:

$$\overline{\Phi} = \int_{-b}^{+b} h \mu \overline{H_x(z)} dz = \frac{2\delta h \mu}{1 + j} H_0 \tanh(1 + j) \frac{b}{\delta} \quad (2)$$

where μ is the macroscopic low frequency magnetic permeability. Considering a coil with N turns wound around a core with axial length d , $d/2b$ laminations, and assuming an infinitely small insulation thickness between iron sheets, the impedance of the coil can be expressed by the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \overline{Z} = \frac{\overline{U}}{\overline{I}} = \frac{j}{1+j} \frac{\delta d h \mu \omega}{\mathcal{L} b} N^2 \tanh(1 + j) \frac{b}{\delta} \\ \overline{U} = j \omega N \overline{\Phi} \\ \overline{I} = \frac{H_0 \mathcal{L}}{N} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{L} represents the mean length of the magnetic field flux lines, ω is the pulsation, \overline{U} is the induced voltage in the

Fig. 2. Normalized amplitude for L_{ac}/k and R_{ac}/k with $2b = 0.5$ mm, $\sigma_{iron} = 2.38$ MS/m

Fig. 3. Low frequency hysteresis characteristic quadrant including different rotor positions (i.e., RP1, RP2, and RP3) and small amplitude high-frequency minor loops

winding and \bar{I} the current creating the main magnetic field. By separating the real and imaginary parts:

$$\begin{cases} L_{ac} = \omega \frac{hd\mu N^2}{\mathcal{L}} \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\sinh(\xi) + \sin(\xi)}{\cosh(\xi) + \cos(\xi)} \\ R_{ac} = \omega^2 \frac{hd\mu N^2}{\mathcal{L}} \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\sinh(\xi) - \sin(\xi)}{\cosh(\xi) + \cos(\xi)} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\xi = 2b/\delta$, which relates the field penetration depth to the lamination thickness. By defining the constant $k = hdN^2/\mathcal{L}$ it is possible to define the direct dependency of L_{ac} and R_{ac} on the relative permeability and the frequency. Figure 2 shows the normalized amplitude of L_{ac}/k and R_{ac}/k . The figure shows how the frequency dominates the value of both reactance and resistance (i.e., imaginary and real part of the impedance respectively). However, the relative permeability influences the value of both terms almost linearly. Thus, the effect of the iron core is not negligible even if the flux penetration is limited at high frequencies.

The macroscopic relative permeability (i.e., μ_r) value depends on the direct excitation of the iron magnetic domains and thus, on the magnetic flux density in the considered

iron geometry. For PMSM small signal frequency sweep in standstill conditions (utilized in off-line SFRA), the rotor is at a fixed position imposing a dc field in the iron core of the stator coils. Thus, the value of the permeability for a single coil impedance will vary depending on the rotor position along the machine air gap. The more saturated the iron core is, the lower the macroscopic permeability and the lower the impedance of the single conductors within a coil. Figure 3 exemplifies the minor loops traced by the small signal injection for different rotor positions. The macroscopic relative permeability is considered isotropic without consideration of the flux excitation direction.

III. PMSM STUDY

A. Magnetostatic FEA

The main objective of this subsection is to link the variation of the macroscopic relative permeability with the different rotor positions of the machine under study. Table I shows the main machine characteristics and Figure 4 depicts the machine cross-section and physical sample. The winding connection is made by connecting four coils in series with one branch for each phase.

TABLE I
CASE STUDY PMSM MACHINE CHARACTERISTICS

Number of poles	8
Number of slots	12
Rated power	4.7 kW
Base speed	6000 rpm
Magnet remanence	1.345 T
BH curve data	M330-50A
Turns/coil	28
Winding connection	Series star

Figure 5 shows a B-field or magnetic flux density contour plot of the stator including the coils forming the machine winding and their tags. The absolute value of the B-field ($|B| = \sqrt{B_x^2 + B_y^2}$) is sampled in three points located in the center of a tooth (i.e., SP-PhA, SP-PhB, SP-PhC) for each phase. The contour plot also highlights that the coils within each phase have the same field distribution at a fixed rotor position. Figure 6 depicts the absolute value of the B-field for the three coils over a range of 90 mechanical degrees, where a periodicity of 45 mechanical degree is observed. The phase-to-phase current flows through coils with different field distributions. Taking into account the winding connection and current path described in Figure 7 (a), it is possible to define the average B-field from a phase-to-phase perspective, which is computed following:

$$|B_{avg}| = \frac{B_{ph,in} + B_{ph,out}}{2} \quad (5)$$

where $B_{ph,in}$ and $B_{ph,out}$ represent the absolute value of the sampled B-field in the coils of the input and output phase respectively. Figure 7 (b) shows the result of equation (5) for different phase combinations over 90 mechanical degree. For the CM configuration, the connection is performed between the three short-circuited phases and ground as described in

Figure 8 (a). The average B-field in this case is provided by the expression:

$$|B_{avg}| = \frac{B_{phA} + B_{phB} + B_{phC}}{3} \quad (6)$$

Figure 8 (b) shows the average B-field in CM configuration variation over 90 mechanical degree. The maximum and minimum B-field values are reduced in comparison with the phase-to-phase configuration.

The relative permeability and thus, the series inductance, resistance and the overall impedance are affected by the field distribution in the different coils. The initial BH magnetization curve (i.e., M330-50A BH characteristic at 50 Hz) provides information on these dependencies. Note that only the trend can be accurately determined since this curve is obtained

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. 8/12 PMSM, 4.7 kW with concentrated winding, (a) Cross-section, (b) physical sample

Fig. 5. B-field contour plot in the case study machine stator for rotor position $\theta' = 0$, d-axis aligned with phase A magnetic axis

for one magnetic direction and it does not represent the real hysteresis characteristic of the material. The relative permeability is higher for lower values of B-field (i.e., the

Fig. 6. B-field absolute value samples in points SP-PhA, SP-PhB, SP-PhC with respect to the rotor position

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Winding connection schematic with current path for different phase connections, (b) Average B-field absolute value for different phase connections with respect to the rotor position

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. (a) Winding connection schematic with current path for CM connection, (b) Average B-field absolute value for CM configuration

relative permeability is defined from the BH curve slope in different regions). Figure 9 shows the initial magnetization BH curve and the locations of the low-frequency operating points for different rotor positions. From the figure it is evident that the higher the B-field in the coils, the lower the low-frequency relative permeability of the material and the lower the impedance experienced by the phase-to-phase current. For the CM configuration, little variation of the impedance is expected when affected by inductive terms since the difference between maximum and minimum average B-field is negligible. The phase-to-phase average B-field difference is approximately 0.6 T, while for CM connection it is approximately 0.08 T.

B. Experimental investigation

The present section describes the experimental set-up and the results of the investigation at hand. The broadband impedance measurement is performed by utilizing an auto-balancing bridge impedance analyser (Agilent 4294A) in the frequency spectrum ranging from 100 Hz to 10 MHz. The test is performed by changing the rotor position while measuring the impedance between different phase combinations. The rotor has 8 poles, which indicates that the d-axis of the rotor will be aligned with a single coil axis every 45 degree. However, the rotor position range is extended up to 90 degree for data redundancy and reliability. The rotor position is swept in intervals of 15 degree and thus, seven different samples are taken for each phase combination. Figure 10 shows the machine under test with three different rotor positions while measuring impedance. The rotor position cannot be accurately defined in some cases because of the increased cogging torque when two phases are connected and some impedance offset is expected for some rotor positions that should provide coincident impedance values. The phases are now tagged as A'-B'-C' and they are not necessary coincident with the phases from Figure 5. Three measurement connections are implemented in order to obtain the phase-to-phase impedance between the three different phase combinations.

Figure 11 shows the measurement results obtained for the different phase combinations and rotor positions. The

Fig. 9. M330-50A initial magnetization BH curve at 50 Hz and operating points for the PhA-PhB estimated average B-field for different rotor positions

Fig. 10. Different rotor positions for impedance measurement, (a) $\theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\theta = 45^\circ$, (c) $\theta = 90^\circ$

behaviour of the curves is mainly inductive up to a resonance point located around 600 kHz. From that point on, the impedance curve behaves in a dominant capacitive manner. The focus is placed in the inductive part of the impedance since it is mainly influenced by the series resistance and inductance. An evident amplitude offset is observed between different rotor positions for all phase combinations. The offset between different rotor positions defines two clusters of curves, one of them around a higher impedance value and a second one located at lower amplitude values. The details in Figure 11 show the curves corresponding to each rotor position in the different amplitude and phase clusters. Regarding phase variations, very little disagreement is observed over the inductive part of the curve. The main differences in the phase curve are located around the resonant point (i.e., in the band 100 kHz - 1 MHz). The phase traces follow two different trends in this band and they are grouped following the trend observed in the amplitude curves. The two amplitude clusters comprise different rotor position traces depending on the phase combination. It is observed that the traces in the higher amplitude cluster are always separated by a space of 45 mechanical degree. In this way, traces corresponding to 0° , 45° and 90° ; 15° and 60° ; and 30° and 75° are grouped in the higher amplitude cluster for the measurement between phases A'B', A'C', and B'C' respectively.

The 45 mechanical degree separation in the high impedance clusters coincides with the low average B-field repeatability over the considered 90 mechanical degree. Table II shows the comparison between the impedance amplitude measurement at 10 kHz and the phase-to-phase average B-field obtained in the FEA simulation. From these results it is evident that the high impedance results are associated with lower average B-field and viceversa. Note that the tagging of the phases between simulation and physical samples does not necessarily coincide. The links between analytical exploration, FEA analysis and real machine measurement explain the physical phenomenon relating rotor field and broadband phase impedance variation over its inductive band.

Figure 12 shows the relative deviation caused by the rotor position variation for the three different phase-to-phase connections. The relative deviation is computed with respect the mean value for all the considered rotor positions following the

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 11. Measured PMSM broadband phase impedance for different rotor positions and phase combinations with details, (a) Phases A'B', (b) Phases A'C', (c) Phases B'C'

following expression:

$$\frac{Z_{max} - Z_{min}}{(Z_{max} + Z_{min})/2} \quad (7)$$

where Z_{max} and Z_{min} represent the maximum and minimum impedance absolute value respectively among all rotor posi-

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION VALUES FOR IMPEDANCE AMPLITUDE AND AVERAGE PHASE-TO-PHASE B-FIELD FOR DIFFERENT ROTOR POSITIONS

Experimental Measurement at 10 kHz			
Rotor position [deg.]	PhA'B' $ Z [\Omega]$	PhA'C' $ Z [\Omega]$	PhB'C' $ Z [\Omega]$
0	208.58	159.26	157.08
15	155.03	207.54	157.75
30	153.83	161.12	207.4
45	207.56	156.83	155.84
60	153.94	208.61	157.91
75	157.5	160.93	207.89
90	207.86	157.91	150.97
FEA magnetostatic simulation			
Rotor position [deg.]	PhAB avg. $ B [T]$	PhAC avg. $ B [T]$	PhBC avg. $ B [T]$
0	1.217	1.216	0.842
15	1.129	0.834	1.216
30	0.838	1.215	1.214
45	1.217	1.216	0.842
60	1.219	0.844	1.216
75	0.838	1.215	1.214
90	1.217	1.216	0.842

Fig. 12. Rotor position induced relative deviation for different phase-to-phase broadband impedances for the PMSM under study

tions at a single frequency point. Differences between different phases are observed mainly in the inductive dominant band, while the minimum deviation is located when the impedance becomes fully capacitive. Note that light deviations are observed between phases even if the location of the conductors is the same for all machine coils in the case of the concentrated winding PMSM. The cause for these deviations may be due to the space discretization while swiping the rotor position. Nevertheless, the deviation is constant over the inductive band and it is reduced for frequencies close to the resonant point around 600 kHz. The maximum relative deviation is observed for the phase connection BC at 15.5 kHz (i.e., 31.5 %) while the minimum is found in the capacitive band around 5 MHz (i.e., 0.3 %).

The measurement of the CM impedance for different rotor positions is shown in figure 13. The traces are mainly coincident due to the capacitive dominance of the curve. Nevertheless, small variations are observed in the resonant points since these are lightly influenced by the inductance and resistance variation. No evident clustering is observed for these variations.

Fig. 13. Measured broadband CM impedance for different rotor positions

Thus, it is demonstrated that the CM impedance presents very little sensitivity to the variation of the rotor position. This may not be true for machines where the winding-to-rotor parasitic capacitance plays a significant role.

IV. INDUCTION MACHINE STUDY

This section presents an experimental investigation to elucidate the reasons behind the dependence of the broadband impedance on the rotor position for machines with absence of strong rotor magnetic field and saliency. To this aim, two different induction machines with different rotor types are selected for the analysis. The first specimen is a squirrel cage induction machine with cylindrical rotor, while the second consists of a wound rotor induction machine with slotted rotor. Both machines possess a fully pitched single layer distributed winding. Table III shows the main characteristics of both machines and figure 14 (a) and (b) depicts the two machines under study with a high level of detail.

TABLE III
INDUCTION MOTOR CHARACTERISTICS

	Squirrel cage machine	Wound rotor machine
Number of poles	4	4
Rated power	1.1 kW	0.6 kW
Rated speed	1440 rpm	1450 rpm
Power factor	0.78	0.8
Rated voltage	230/400 V	220/380 V
Rotor slots	28	24
Stator slots	36	36

The magnetic remanence of induction machines is a possible cause for inductance variation [19]. In addition, Kang et al. [17] report differences in rotor residual fluxes for open-slot and closed slot induction machines (i.e., wound rotor machine in figure 14 (b) and squirrel cage machine of figure 14 (a) respectively). To test the presence of rotor remanent flux, an open circuit test is performed, where a prime mover is utilized to rotate the induction machines under study. The prime mover consists of an induction motor with 4 poles fed at mains frequency (i.e., 50 Hz). Figure 14 (c) shows the measured voltage between one phase and the neutral point

Fig. 14. (a) Squirrel cage machine details, (b) Assembled wound rotor machine detail, (c) Induced back emf measured between phase and neutral points

of the studied machines. Low voltage amplitudes at nearly 50 Hz are observed, which indicates the presence of a remanent rotor flux coincident with the number of pole pairs of the machine. However, the observed amplitudes are small valued, corresponding to the 0.97% and 0.77% of the maximum rated voltage for the squirrel cage and wound rotor machines respectively. The presence of a remanent flux coincident with the number of pole pairs represents a feasible cause for the dependence of the broadband impedance variation with the rotor position.

The analysis is carried out separately for both machines. The experimental equipment to obtain the broadband impedance response in this case is a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) with a bandwidth between 5kHz and 3 GHz (Rohde & Schwarz ZNL3). The measurement principle is slightly different compared with the more classical impedance analyzer but with a similar performance in the frequency band of interest, which is set between 5 kHz and 1 MHz to capture the main resonance points [26]. The procedure is defined as explained in Section III-B, where the rotor position is swept while measuring the impedance for different phase combinations. The number of poles for both machines is 4 and thus, 7 different points are now defined between 0 and 180 mechanical degree to capture two electrical periods. The phase-to-phase broadband impedance is measured in order to generalize for machines with no accessible neutral point.

A. Squirrel cage rotor

This subsection is aimed to present and analyze the broadband phase-to-phase impedance response for the squirrel cage rotor induction machine. Figure 15 shows the comparison

between different phase combinations for 7 different rotor positions. The primary resonance occurs at approximately 10 kHz, with multiple resonances and anti-resonances identified within the frequency range spanning 10 kHz to 400 kHz. Beyond 400 kHz the impedance transitions to a predominantly capacitive nature. The rotor position influences the inductive band and the first resonance and anti-resonance points (i.e., located at 10 kHz and 17 kHz respectively). A light clustering is observed for different traces in the inductive band. This clustering is not constant for all phases as observed in the PMSM sample. Nevertheless, traces spaced 90 mechanical degree are observed coincident or close to each other (e.g.,

Fig. 15. Measured squirrel cage machine broadband phase impedance for different rotor positions and phase combinations with details, (a) Phases UV, (b) Phases UW, (c) Phases VW

Fig. 16. Rotor position induced relative deviation for different phase-to-phase broadband impedances for the squirrel cage induction machine under study

figure 15 (a) traces at 150 and 60 degree, and figure 15 (b) traces at 0, 90, and 180 degree). These follow the same trend observed for the PMSM machine, where traces are clustered for coincident electrical positions.

Figure 16 shows the relative deviation computed following equation 7. In this case, a constant deviation over the inductive band is present as observed for the PMSM case. Once again, a light deviation (i.e., approximately 4%) is identified due to the coarse spatial discretization of the rotor position sweep. The main difference with respect the PMSM machine lays on the deviation in the main resonant points where the sensitivity to the rotor position is evident. Note that the transition from inductive to capacitive in the case of this machine sample is smoother than for the PMSM case, which is translated on an augmented impact of the inductive terms in the resonant points. The relative deviation is very reduced when the impedance becomes fully capacitive independently of the phase connection and the rotor position. The maximum and minimum deviation correspond to the 23.9% and 0.4% located in the primary resonance point and capacitive area respectively.

B. Wound rotor

This subsection analyzes the experimental phase-to-phase broadband impedance measurement for the wound-rotor machine. The measurement is performed with the three phases of the rotor in short-circuit. Figure 17 shows the acquired impedance curves. For this scenario, a main resonance is observed around 14 kHz. The effect of the rotor swipe is not clearly observed in the inductive band, and figure 17 details show very little clustering effect between traces. However, the resonances located in the band between 40 kHz and 200 kHz show some deviations which are not observed in the squirrel cage case. Figure 18 shows the relative deviation between traces for all phase combinations. In this case, the greater deviation (i.e., 14.81%) is observed within a capacitive dominant band. This may indicate a non-negligible influence of the winding-to-rotor capacitance. The relative deviation due to the rotor position variation is once again negligible when the impedance becomes fully capacitive. Nevertheless, significant differences are observed in the inductive band and

Fig. 17. Measured wound rotor machine broadband phase impedance for different rotor positions and phase combinations with details, (a) Phases UV, (b) Phases UW, (c) Phases VW

first resonant point even if these do not represent the maximum deviation in this case.

V. DISCUSSION

The main contribution of the work lays on the study of the rotor position influence on the repeatability of the SFRA measurements for different machine types. Particularly, the paper provides a comprehensive analysis regarding the effect of the rotor DC field. This field is often observed as material residual flux in machines with absence of rotor magnets such as induction machines. For the PMSM under study, it is demonstrated that the rotor position influence is minimum for the CM configuration due to its predominant capacitive

Fig. 18. Rotor position induced relative deviation for different phase-to-phase broadband impedances for the wound rotor induction machine under study

behaviour and the reduced average B-field variation under DC field excitation. A significant variation is observed over the inductive frequency band in a phase-to-phase configuration for the three machines under study, independently of the winding type (i.e., concentrated or full pitch distributed windings). Figure 19 shows the three dimensional representation of the broadband phase-to-phase impedance including rotor position variation. The influence of the number of poles on the first resonance ripple is easily observed, which is closely related to the DC rotor field independently of the frequency of excitation. For the considered mechanical angle span (i.e., two electrical periods) two maxima and minima are observed for all three specimens, elucidating a dominant electrical periodicity of the variation. These observations are aligned with [19], where the authors report inductance variation with electrical periodicity at 1.2 kHz for squirrel cage induction machines including degaussed specimens and machines with inherent remanence. The PMSM shows a strong trace clustering for rotor positions spaced one electrical period. This clustering is slightly observed for the squirrel cage specimen and almost negligible for the wound rotor induction machine. The maximum relative deviation with respect the mean of all rotor position traces is observed in different points depending on the machine under study. Nonetheless, the deviation in the inductive band is correlated with the strength of the rotor field. The PMSM exhibited a maximum deviation of 31.53% when sampled at 10 kHz, while the squirrel cage and wound rotor machines showed maximum inductive deviations of 17.04% (sampled at 7.3 kHz) and 9.6% (sampled at 9 kHz) respectively.

The variation of the inductance depending on the rotor position in a broad frequency band may possess a multi-source nature. The flux penetration is limited for high frequencies, which strongly limits inductive couplings across the laminated core. This strongly depends on the excitation frequency and on the core local permeability and conductivity [20]. Moreover, remanence in induction machines prevents the flux penetration in the rotor as reported in [17]. Nevertheless, inductive couplings between phases and rotor may contribute to the electrical periodicity of the overall measured inductance [27], mostly when iron sections are not continuous along the cylindrical rotor periphery. Another factor that does not exhibit

Fig. 19. Phase-to-phase broadband impedance depending on the rotor position comparison, (a) PMSM, (b) squirrel cage induction machine, (c) wound rotor induction machine

electrical periodicity but may affect the inductance is the presence of inherent small-valued mixed eccentricity, which influences the value of the stator phase self-inductance [28].

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presented a thorough investigation of the rotor position effect on the broadband stator impedance for different machine types and winding connections. Firstly, an analytical exploration of the variables affecting the broadband impedance of a coil with laminated core was performed. Secondly, a PMSM case study machine was analysed in depth including magnetostatic FEA and experimental measurements. The same effect was experimentally studied for two different induction machines including different rotor topologies. A thorough discussion of the results across the three studied specimens is provided in section V. Note that the rotor-induced relative deviation may exhibit variations across different machines. Therefore, it is imperative to conduct an analysis of this deviation before undertaking a diagnosis, particularly if the impact of the rotor falls out the diagnosis object and disassembly is not possible or cost-effective. This analysis should be performed after newly assembled machines have undergone nominal operation and inherent material remanence is established. The rotor position effect may be critical for the detection of stator inter-turn short circuits and insulation ageing where their impact in the electrical signature is reduced and may be masked by the rotor influence. The detailed study of broadband inductive couplings represents a future research step which will elucidate the mutual coupling contribution and the validity of stator SFRA to diagnose faults with inductive coupling nature (e.g., rotor related faults).

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE, "Ieee guide for the application and interpretation of frequency response analysis for oil-immersed transformers," *Proceedings of the IEEE Std C57.149-2012*, pp. 1–72, 2013.
- [2] M. Florkowski and J. Furgal, "Detection of winding faults in electrical machines using the frequency response analysis method," *Measurement Science and Technology*, vol. 15, no. 10, p. 2067, 2004.
- [3] T. G. Vilhekar, M. S. Ballal, and B. S. Umre, "Application of sweep frequency response analysis for the detection of winding faults in induction motor," in *IECON 2016-42nd Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1458–1463.
- [4] S. M. Al-Ameri, Z. Abdul-Malek, A. A. Salem, Z. A. Noorden, A. A. Alawady, M. F. M. Yousof, M. I. Mosaad, A. Abu-Siada, and H. A. Thabit, "Frequency response analysis for three-phase star and delta induction motors: Pattern recognition and fault analysis using statistical indicators," *Machines*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 106, 2023.
- [5] L. Lamarre and P. Picher, "Impedance characterization of hydro generator stator windings and preliminary results of fra analysis," in *Conference record of the 2008 IEEE international symposium on electrical insulation*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 227–230.
- [6] W. C. Sant'Ana, C. P. Salomon, G. Lambert-Torres, L. E. B. da Silva, E. L. Bonaldi, L. E. d. L. de Oliveira, and J. G. B. da Silva, "A survey on statistical indexes applied on frequency response analysis of electric machinery and a trend based approach for more reliable results," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 137, pp. 26–33, 2016.
- [7] N. J. Jameson, M. H. Azarian, and M. Pecht, "Impedance-based condition monitoring for insulation systems used in low-voltage electromagnetic coils," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 5, pp. 3748–3757, 2017.
- [8] F. Blázquez, C. Platero, E. Rebollo, and F. Blázquez, "Field-winding fault detection in synchronous machines with static excitation through frequency response analysis," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 73, pp. 229–239, 2015.
- [9] A. Mugarra, C. A. Platero, J. A. Martínez, and U. Albizuri-Txurruka, "Validity of frequency response analysis (fra) for diagnosing large salient poles of synchronous machines," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 226–234, 2019.
- [10] H. Mayora, R. Alvarez, G. Bossio, and E. Calo, "Condition assessment of rotating electrical machines using sfra-a survey," in *2021 IEEE Electrical Insulation Conference (EIC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 26–29.
- [11] W. C. Sant'Ana, C. P. Salomon, G. Lambert-Torres, L. E. B. da Silva, E. L. Bonaldi, L. E. d. L. de Oliveira, and J. G. B. da Silva, "Early detection of insulation failures on electric generators through online frequency response analysis," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 140, pp. 337–343, 2016.
- [12] W. C. Sant'Ana, G. Lambert-Torres, E. L. Bonaldi, B. R. Gama, T. G. Zacarias, I. A. d. S. Areias, D. d. A. Arantes, F. d. O. Assuncao, M. M. Campos, and F. M. Steiner, "Online frequency response analysis of electric machinery through an active coupling system based on power electronics," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, p. 8057, 2021.
- [13] G. Bucci, F. Ciancetta, and E. Fiorucci, "Apparatus for online continuous diagnosis of induction motors based on the sfra technique," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 7, pp. 4134–4144, 2019.
- [14] C. A. Platero, F. Blázquez, P. Frias, and D. Ramírez, "Influence of rotor position in fra response for detection of insulation failures in salient-pole synchronous machines," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 671–676, 2011.
- [15] B. Mirafzal, G. L. Skibinski, R. M. Tallam, D. W. Schlegel, and R. A. Lukaszewski, "Universal induction motor model with low-to-high frequency-response characteristics," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 1233–1246, 2007.
- [16] W. C. Sant'Ana, G. Lambert-Torres, L. E. B. da Silva, E. L. Bonaldi, L. E. d. L. de Oliveira, C. P. Salomon, and J. G. B. da Silva, "Influence of rotor position on the repeatability of frequency response analysis

measurements on rotating machines and a statistical approach for more meaningful diagnostics,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 133, pp. 71–78, 2016.

- [17] T.-j. Kang, J. Hong, S. B. Lee, Y.-W. Yoon, D.-H. Hwang, and D. Kang, “The influence of the rotor on surge pd testing of low voltage ac motor stator windings,” *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 762–769, 2013.
- [18] K. Vanthuyne, M. Gulec, and P. Sergeant, “High-frequency motor modelling: Parameter variation due to manufacturing,” in *2022 International Conference on Electrical Machines (ICEM)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 821–826.
- [19] D. L. McKinnon and H. A. Smolleck, “Influence of rotor residual flux on the measurement of inductance and its possible use as an impending fault indicator,” in *IEEE EMCW 2004 Technical Conference*, 2004.
- [20] D. Roger, E. Napieralska-Juszczak, and A. Hennenon, “High frequency extension of non-linear models of laminated cores,” *COMPEL-The international journal for computation and mathematics in electrical and electronic engineering*, 2006.
- [21] J. E. Ruiz-Sarrio, J. A. Antonino-Daviu, and C. Martis, “An investigation of the rotor position influence on the broadband phase impedance - application to sfra diagnosis,” in *2023 IEEE 14th International Symposium on Diagnostics for Electrical Machines, Power Electronics and Drives (SDEMPED)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 134–140.
- [22] N. Boucenna, F. Costa, S. Hlioui, and B. Revol, “Strategy for predictive modeling of the common-mode impedance of the stator coils in ac machines,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 12, pp. 7360–7371, 2016.
- [23] J. E. Ruiz-Sarrio, F. Chauvicourt, J. Gyselincx, and C. Martis, “Impedance modeling oriented toward the early prediction of high-frequency response for permanent magnet synchronous machines,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 4548–4557, 2022.
- [24] K. Maki, “Automated technique for building high-frequency equivalent circuits of motors based on electromagnetic field analysis,” *Electrical Engineering in Japan*, vol. 215, no. 3, p. e23395, 2022.
- [25] J. Lammeraner and M. Štafl, *Eddy currents*. Iliffe books, 1966.
- [26] M. Horibe, “Performance comparisons between impedance analyzers and vector network analyzers for impedance measurement below 100 mhz frequency,” in *2017 89th ARFTG Microwave Measurement Conference (ARFTG)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–4.
- [27] H. A. Toliyat, M. S. Arefeen, and A. G. Parlos, “A method for dynamic simulation of air-gap eccentricity in induction machines,” *IEEE transactions on industry applications*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 910–918, 1996.
- [28] H. H. Safa, M. Ebrahimi, A. Davoudi, and A. Pouramin, “Analytical derivation of induction motors inductances under eccentricity conditions,” *Progress In Electromagnetics Research B*, vol. 60, pp. 95–110, 2014.

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